

Fig. 3. Effect of stearic acid and zinc oxide in accelerated low-sulphur reclaim compounds.

exotherms (which not necessarily are solely due to curing) are concerned, on addition of stearic acid and then zinc oxide peak height decreases slowly and sharply respectively in high- and low- sulphur compounds. These peak height values in each of the three low-sulphur systems are much higher than those of the corresponding high- sulphur compounds. In low-sulphur compounds fractional peak area^{2,3}, as indicated above, diminishes by a small extent on addition of stearic acid and falls sharply when zinc oxide is also added, but in high-sulphur compounds such area does not show appreciable difference in presence or in absence of these additives. Also such areas in low-sulphur compounds are found to be greater than those of the corresponding high-sulphur systems. Differences observed either in the initiation temperatures (T_i) or in the peak temperatures (T_p) are not significant in presence or in absence of stearic acid and zinc oxide, in case of high-sulphur compounds. On the other hand, in low-sulphur compounds T_i at first decreases nominally on addition of stearic acid, but again increases on addition of zinc oxide along with stearic acid, whereas T_p , although does not show appreciable change on addition of stearic acid, falls sharply when zinc oxide is also added. T_i and T_p in each of the set of the three high-sulphur systems are, however, higher and lower respectively than those of the corresponding low-sulphur systems. Peak slope remains almost the same in presence or in absence of stearic acid and zinc oxide, but compared to the low-sulphur systems, the high-sulphur ones exhibit somewhat higher slope values.

Subsequent to the above initial exotherms the thermal patterns do not show significant characteristics in high-sulphur compounds, but in low-sulphur systems a secondary peak is observed, its sharpness gradually diminishing on addition of stearic acid and then zinc oxide.

Detailed works are in progress and will be published later on.

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Temperature Coefficient of E.M.F. of the Cell $\text{Co} | \text{Co-Soap(s)}, \text{K-Soap}, \text{Cu-Soap(s)} | \text{Cu}$ and the Entropy of Reactions

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IN spite of the fact that most of the heavy metal salts of higher fatty acids are insoluble in water, metal-metal soap electrodes have been little studied. Kolthoff and Johnson¹ employed a silver-silver laurate electrode for measuring laurate ion activity in aqueous solutions of potassium laurate. For quite some time we are engaged in carrying out

TABLE 1. E.M.F. OF THE CELLS, TEMPERATURE COEFFICIENT OF E.M.F. AND ΔG , ΔH AND ΔS OR THE CELL REACTIONS

Cell reaction	Cell E.M.F. at 303 K <i>E</i> , volts	dE/dT volts deg ⁻¹	ΔG 303 K cal	ΔH 303 K cal	ΔS at 303 K cal deg ⁻¹
$\text{Co} + (\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{23}\text{COO})_2\text{Cu} \rightleftharpoons (\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{23}\text{COO})_2\text{Co} + \text{Cu}$	0.240	-0.00113	-11070	-26900	-52.26
$\text{Co} + (\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{27}\text{COO})_2\text{Cu} \rightleftharpoons (\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{27}\text{COO})_2\text{Co} + \text{Cu}$	0.250	-0.00095	-11530	-24800	-43.81
$\text{Co} + (\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{31}\text{COO})_2\text{Cu} \rightleftharpoons (\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{31}\text{COO})_2\text{Co} + \text{Cu}$	0.255	-0.00088	-11760	-24100	-40.74
$\text{Co} + (\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{35}\text{COO})_2\text{Cu} \rightleftharpoons (\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{35}\text{COO})_2\text{Co} + \text{Cu}$	0.268	-0.00081	-12360	-23690	-37.41

systematic studies on a number of metal-metal soap electrode systems using metals like cobalt, nickel, copper etc. and have reported in recent communications on the suitability of cobalt-cobalt soap², copper-copper soap^{3,4} and nickel-nickel soap⁵ electrodes for studying detergent anion activity variation in aqueous solutions of potassium soaps. These studies were later extended to determine the values of ΔG , ΔH and ΔS for the reaction of the type $\text{Cu} + 2\text{AgD} \rightleftharpoons \text{CuD}_2 + 2\text{Ag}$ (where D stands for laurate, myristate, palmitate and stearate) from E.M.F. measurements⁶. The present communication is a further study of metal-metal soap electrode systems and reports on the values of ΔG , ΔH and ΔS , calculated from E.M.F. measurements of the cell $\text{Co} | \text{CoD}_2(\text{s}), \text{KD}(\text{c}), \text{CuD}_2(\text{s}) | \text{Cu}$ for the reaction $\text{Co} + \text{CuD}_2 \rightleftharpoons \text{CoD}_2 + \text{Cu}$.

Experimental

Reagents :

Potassium laurate, myristate, palmitate and stearate were prepared by the method adopted earlier². Cobalt and copper soaps were prepared by direct metathesis^{2,3}.

Cobalt and copper electrodes :

Cobalt and copper electrodes were prepared by electrodeposition on platinum wires by the method already described^{2,3}.

E.M.F. measurements :

A Cambridge portable potentiometer was used for the E.M.F. measurements of the cell

at different temperatures in a water thermostat. The cell vessel employed was of H type. The two limbs of the cell were provided with cobalt and copper electrodes. The cell contained aqueous solutions of potassium soap saturated with cobalt and copper soaps. Some solid metal soaps were always added to the cell to ensure that the potassium soap solution was always saturated with respect to metal soaps.

Results and Discussion

The reaction taking place in the cell for the passage of 2F of electricity is as follows :

Since both the electrodes involved in the cell under consideration are reversible with respect to the detergent anion, the E.M.F. of the cells should be independent of the concentration of potassium soap. It was found that the cell E.M.F. was independent of the concentration of potassium soap solution. The following equations were used for calculating, ΔG , ΔH and ΔS

$$\Delta G = -nEF$$

$$\Delta G - \Delta H = T \left[\frac{d(\Delta G)}{dT} \right]$$

or,

$$-nEF = \Delta H - nFT \left(\frac{dE}{dT} \right)$$

$$\Delta S = nF \left(\frac{dE}{dT} \right)$$

The values of the E.M.F. of cells at 303 °K, the temperature coefficient of the E.M.F. and the values of ΔG , ΔH and ΔS for the cell reactions are given in Table 1.

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